

Works in Progress

An Immunomodulative Formulation with Allergic Reaction Inhibitive Properties

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Description

A COMPOSITION FOR THE TREATMENT OF ALLERGIC REACTIONS

Technical Field

The invention relates to a composition formed for the treatment of allergic reactions.

State of the Art

Histamine is a substance, which is present in most human and animal cells and causes the reactions called allergy when it goes out of the cell for various reasons. Levvis, at the experiments he conducted with histamine on animals early in this century, noticed the occurrence of a red dot in the skin at the site of injection, a wide red zone around this dot and a swelling in the form of a wide edema around said zone (triple response). In addition, when he injected histamine at higher doses to guinea pigs and rabbits, he observed the occurrence of a shock resembling the tissue damage. The cell lysis has been accepted to increase the production of histamine especially in the lungs and the skin and initiate the antigen-antibody reaction.

The substances that cause general tissue damage (trypsin, peptone, snake or bee venom, detergents), macromolecular substances (horse serum, dextran), endotoxins and some drugs (epinephrine, morphine, codeine, tubocurarine, etc.) release histamine and cause allergic reactions. Subsequent researches have shown that histamine acts like a local hormone and reduces the blood pressure as well as playing a role in the transmission in the nervous system (neurotransmitter) and affecting some receptors (H1 and H2 receptors). Accordingly, some of the histamine-associated effects such as the increased gastric secretion mediated by H2 receptors, increased heart rate and itching may be eliminated with some medicaments.

The substances that prevent the effects of histamine are referred to as antihistamines. Antihistamines prevent the emergence of such reactions, rather than treating them. In cases such as severe allergy and anaphylactic shock, the patient is immediately injected the drugs such as adrenaline and cortisone. Afterwards, the treatment may be continued with one of a great number of antihistaminic drugs.

The invention no. ES19990001232 entitled "Indolylpiperidine derivatives as antihistaminic and antiallergic agents" relates to a novel indolylpiperidine compound and the pharmaceutically acceptable salts thereof having antihistaminic activity and antiallergic activity and providing benefits as a medication for the treatment of bronchial asthma, allergic rhinitis, conjunctivitis, dermatosis, urticaria and the like.

The invention no. EP19960810436 entitled "Topical composition comprising a combination of terpenoid compounds and antihistaminic compounds" relates to topical pharmaceutical compositions containing a mixture of a terpenoid compound and an antihistaminic compound for the treatment of the allergic and inflammatory skin diseases as well as the topical use of an antihistaminic compound in combination with a terpenoid compound (for the manufacture of a medicament).

The invention no. ES19960001236 entitled "Novel benzimidazole derivatives with antihistaminic activity" discloses novel benzimidazole derivatives of the respective formula and the pharmacologically acceptable acids or bases and additional salts thereof. In the formula, R1 is hydrogen or a short-chain hydrocarbon group such as methyl, ethyl, isopropyl, cyclopropyl or vinyl; R2 is a group selected from CH₂OH, COOH, COOR and 4,4-dimethyl-2-oxazoliny; and R3 is a short-chain alkyl group as defined above. In addition, the preparation of these compositions, which have a significant H₁ antihistaminic and antiallergic activity and which do not cause adverse effects on the central nervous system and cardiovascular system, are also described.

As a result, the presence of the need for a composition for the treatment of the allergic reactions and the inadequacy of the existing solutions have made it necessary to perform an improvement in the relevant art.

Object of the Invention

In order to eliminate the disadvantages of the state of the art, an object of the invention is to provide for the treatment of the allergic reactions.

Another object of the invention is to suppress IL-6 and IL-4 to suppress the allergic reactions.

Another object of the invention is to suppress the pro-inflammatory cytokines such as tnf-alpha, interferon gamma and nf-kappa B and signal molecules.

Another object of the invention is to suppress the production of immunoglobulin E to provide improvement in the allergic reactions.

Another object of the invention is to provide the activity that increases the breathing capacity and the anti-bronchoconstrictive activity, owing to the resemblance with the testosterone derivatives.

In order to achieve the aforesaid advantages, the invention is a composition for the treatment of the allergic reactions, said composition being obtained by the components selected from the group comprising 1,3 colforsin acetate and Cissus Quadrangularis extract that are used individually or in combinations.

The structural and characteristic features and all the advantages of the invention will become more clearly understood from the detailed description provided below and therefore, the evaluation must be made taking this detailed description into consideration.

Detailed Description of the Invention

The invention is a composition for the treatment of allergic reactions. The composition according to the invention contains 1,3 colforsin acetate and Cissus Quadrangularis extract.

Cissus Qaudrangularis extract (contains 20-40% ketosterone), one of the ingredients of the composition according to the invention, suppresses IL-6 and IL-4 to suppress the allergic reactions. Cissus Qaudrangularis extract (contains 20-40% ketosterone) also suppresses the pro-inflammatory cytokines such as tnf-alpha, interferon gamma and nf-kappa B and signal molecules.

Cissus Qaudrangularis extract (contains 20-40% ketosterone) also suppresses the production of immunoglobulin E to provide improvement in the allergic reactions. Moreover, the ketosterones obtained from Cissus Quadrangularis provide the activity that increases the breathing capacity and the anti-bronchoconstrictive activity, owing to their resemblance with the testosterone derivates.

Said formulation is obtained by a mixture of the aforesaid components according to the following ratios by weight:

1-99% 1,3 colforsin acetate,

99-1% Cissus Quadrangularis extract (contains 20-40% ketosterone).

The composition is obtained from the aforesaid components selected from the aforesaid group and used according to the mentioned weight ratio ranges individually or in combinations.

Said invention also encompasses the use of said composition for the treatment of the allergic reactions and the manufacture thereof for this purpose.

CLAIMS

1. A composition for the treatment of the allergic reactions, said composition being obtained by the components selected from the group comprising 1,3 colforsin acetate and Cissus Quadrangularis extract that are used individually or in combinations.
2. A composition according to Claim 1 characterized in that it comprises 1-99% by weight 1,3 colforsin acetate.

3. A composition according to Claim 1 characterized in that it comprises 99-1% by weight *Cissus Quadrangularis* extract (contains 20-40% ketosterone).
4. A composition according to Claims 1 and 3 characterized in that *Cissus Quadrangularis* extract comprises 20-40% by weight ketosterone.
5. Use of the components according to Claims 1 to 4 obtained individually or in combinations from the group consisting of 1,3 colforsin acetate and *Cissus Quadrangularis* extract for the manufacture of a composition for the treatment of the allergic reactions.

ABSTRACT

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